

Kinetics of Oxalic Acid-Catalysed Oxidation of Aromatic Azo Compounds by Chromic Acid-Catalytic Kinetic Determination of Microamounts of Oxalic Acid*

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The kinetics of oxidation of some aromatic azo compounds by chromic acid, catalysed by oxalic acid was investigated. The reaction is first order with respect to chromic acid, oxalic acid and substrate. The reaction mixture initiates vinyl polymerization. Activation parameters were evaluated. The catalysed reaction was utilized for developing a kinetic method for the determination of oxalic acid in microgram concentrations with an average error of 1%. The standard deviation, coefficient of variation and percentage error were also calculated.

THE efficacy of oxalic acid as a catalyst for chromic acid oxidations of inorganic compounds has been first noticed by Gopala Rao and coworkers¹, who pressed this into use for developing a number of analytical procedures. Rocek and coworkers² have reported the kinetic investigation of the oxalic acid catalysis of chromic acid oxidation with iodide and ferrous as substrates. We have now found that oxalic acid catalyses the chromic acid oxidation of organic compounds also and in the present paper we report the results of kinetic investigation of oxidation of aromatic azo compounds by chromic acid catalysed by oxalic acid. Basing on this, we have also developed a catalytic kinetic method for the estimation of oxalic acid in microgram amounts.

Experimental

All the materials employed were of analytical reagent grade. The azo compounds were twice recrystallized before use. The course of the reaction was followed by measuring the optical density of the unreacted azo compound at 510 nm where each of the azo compounds has been found to have maximum absorption and obeys Beer's law and all other materials concerned have negligible absorption. The kinetic runs were carried out maintaining the ionic strength constant with sodium perchlorate. Under the experimental conditions employed for the investigation of the catalysed reaction, the rate of the uncatalysed reaction was found to be negligibly small.

Stoichiometry :

The stoichiometry of the reaction was investigated by mixing a known excess of the azo compound with chromic acid in presence and absence of oxalic acid. The amount of azo compound consumed was calculated

from the decrease in the optical density after completion of the reaction (which was indicated by the constancy of the optical density with time). It was found that 4 moles of chromic acid consumed 3 moles of azo compound, both in the presence and absence of oxalic acid, showing that oxalic acid is not consumed in the oxidation during the reaction. Thus the rate acceleration is not due to cooxidation and oxalic acid acts as a catalyst. This is further supported by the fact that under identical conditions the rate of present reaction is very high in comparison with that of chromic acid-oxalic acid reaction showing that oxalic acid consumed through oxidation with chromic acid is negligible.

Product Analysis : The reaction products were run on TLC plate using chloroform-methanol mixture (1:1) as solvent. Two spots were observed. The presence of nitroso group in either of the spots was confirmed by the spot test prescribed by Feigl³. This is also in conformity with the observed mole ratio according to which each molecule of the azo compound loses four electrons or takes up two oxygen atoms during the oxidation.

Initiation of Vinyl Polymerization : The reaction mixture was found to initiate vinyl polymerization indicating that the reaction may proceed through a free radical mechanism.

Results and Discussion

Several kinetic runs were carried out keeping the concentration of chromic acid very high in comparison with that of the azo compound. The plot of log O.D versus time gave a straight line showing that the reaction is first order with respect to each of the azo com-

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pounds. The pseudo first order rate constants, k_1 , were calculated from the slopes of the straight lines.

Effect of varying [Chromic Acid] and [Oxalic Acid] :

The values of k_1 were also determined at different chromic acid and oxalic acid concentrations. Plots of k_1 versus [Chromic Acid] as well as [Oxalic Acid] were straight lines passing through the origin showing that the reaction is first order with respect to chromic acid (Fig. 1) and oxalic acid (Fig. 2).

Effect of varying [Hydrogen ion] :

The pseudo first order rate constants, k_1 , were also determined at different concentrations of perchloric acid by keeping the ionic strength constant with sodium perchlorate. A plot of k_1 versus $[H^+]$ gave a straight line with a positive intercept on k_1 -axis (Fig. 3). This indicates that there are two paths in the reaction—one independent of hydrogen ion concentration and the other with a rate directly proportional to $[H^+]$.

Fig. 1. Plots of k_1 versus $[Cr(VI)]$ [Oxalic acid] = $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, $(HClO_4 = 0.116 M, \mu = 0.116, Temp. = 25 \pm 0.1^\circ C)$
 ○—○ [BADMA] = $1.34 \times 10^{-5} M$
 □—□ [*p*-Nitro BADMA] = $1.26 \times 10^{-5} M$
 ●—● [*p*-Carboxy BADMA] = $2.15 \times 10^{-5} M$
 X—X [*p*-Chloro BADMA] = $1.65 \times 10^{-5} M$
 △—△ [Methyl Orange] = $1.25 \times 10^{-5} M$.

From these results, the experimental rate-law may be expressed as

$$-\frac{d[\text{azo compound}]}{dt} = [HCrO_4^-][OX][\text{Azo Compound}] (k + k'[H^+])$$

Fig. 2. Plots of k_1 versus [Oxalic acid] $[Cr(VI)] = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$; $[HClO_4] = 0.116 M$; $\mu = 0.116$, $Temp. = 25 \pm 0.1^\circ C$
 ○—○ [BADMA] = $1.34 \times 10^{-5} M$
 X—X [*p*-Chloro BADMA] = $1.65 \times 10^{-5} M$
 ●—● [*p*-Carboxy BADMA] = $2.15 \times 10^{-5} M$
 □—□ [*p*-Nitro BADMA] = $1.26 \times 10^{-5} M$
 △—△ [Methyl Orange] = $1.25 \times 10^{-5} M$

Fig. 3. Plots of k_1 versus $[HClO_4]$, $[Cr(VI)] = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$; Oxalic Acid = $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$; $\mu = 2.20$, $Temp. = 25 \pm 0.1^\circ C$
 ○—○ [BADMA] = $1.34 \times 10^{-5} M$
 X—X [*p*-Chloro BADMA] = $1.65 \times 10^{-5} M$
 ●—● [*p*-Carboxy BADMA] = $2.15 \times 10^{-5} M$
 □—□ [*p*-Nitro BADMA] = $1.26 \times 10^{-5} M$
 △—△ [Methyl Orange] = $1.25 \times 10^{-5} M$

Fig. 4. Plot of Δx versus [Oxalic acid], [Methyl orange] = $9.88 \times 10^{-6} M$; [Cr(VI)] = $8.7 \times 10^{-4} M$; [HClO₄] = $0.33 M$ $\mu = 0.33$; Temp. = $30 \pm 0.1^\circ C$.

Activation parameters: The reaction obeys Arrhenius temperature dependence and the values of energy of activation and entropy of activation were calculated. The data were presented in Table 1.

The mechanism leads to the rate-law

$$-\frac{d[\text{azo compound}]}{dt} = K[\text{HCrO}_4^-][\text{OX}][\text{Azo Compound}] / (k+k'[\text{H}^+])$$

The mechanism envisages the formation of 1:1 complex between chromic acid and oxalic which is a better oxidising species than uncomplexed chromium(VI). The greater reactivity of chromium(VI)-oxalic acid complex in comparison with uncomplexed chromium(VI) is presumably due to the presence of the electrophilic carboxyl groups of oxalic acid which render chromium(VI) a better oxidant. It may also be due to the stabilization of the lower valence state of chromium namely, Cr(V), thus increasing the red-ox potential of Cr(VI)/Cr(V) couple. The stabilization of Cr(V) has recently been established by Rocek et al⁹. The authors believe that the mechanism involves one-electron steps basing on the above consideration coupled with the fact that oxalic acid catalyses the oxidation of

TABLE 1—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS

[Cr(VI)] = $1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$; [Oxalic Acid] = 1.0×10^{-3} ; [HClO₄] = $0.116 M$; $\mu = 0.116$

Azo Compound	[Azo Compound] $\times 10^5 M$	E ± 1 k. cal. mole ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger e.u. at 25°C
Benzene azo dimethylaniline C ₆ H ₅ -N=N-C ₆ H ₄ -N(CH ₃) ₂	1.34	11	-21
p-Chlorobenzene azo dimethylaniline Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -N=N-C ₆ H ₄ -N(CH ₃) ₂	1.65	11	-21
p-Carboxy benzene azo dimethylaniline COOH-C ₆ H ₄ -N=N-C ₆ H ₄ -N(CH ₃) ₂	2.15	11	-21
p-Nitro benzene azo dimethylaniline NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -N=N-C ₆ H ₄ -N(CH ₃) ₂	1.26	11	-21
Methyl Orange HSO ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -N=N-C ₆ H ₄ -N(CH ₃) ₂	1.25	11	-21

Mechanism: The types of dependence of rate on the concentrations of substrate, oxalic acid and H⁺ ion are in conformity with the following scheme:

ferroin by chromic acid which must proceed through only one-electron steps^{2b}. This is further supported by the observed initiation of vinyl polymerization by the reaction mixture.

Scheme:

The mechanism also explains the hydrogen ion independent and dependent paths.

Catalytic Kinetic Determination of Oxalic Acid in Microgram amounts :

The authors have employed the oxalic acid catalysed oxidation of methyl orange by chromic acid for the kinetic determination of oxalic acid in microgram amounts (5-15 $\mu\text{g/ml}$). It has been found that the decrease in the optical density Δx exactly for 10 minutes is directly proportional to oxalic acid concentration in the microgram range at an acid concentration of 0.3 M at 30°. Hence, the authors recommend the following procedure for the kinetic determination of oxalic acid. Calculated amounts of methyl orange and perchloric acid to give an overall concentration of $7.3 \times 10^{-6} M$ and 0.3 M respectively, are mixed with a known amount of oxalic acid and water and thermostated. Chromic acid solution is also kept in the same thermostat and after temperature equilibrium is attained, calculated volume of chromic acid, to give an overall concentration of $8.9 \times 10^{-4} M$ (overall volume 25 ml) is to be added, simultaneously starting the stop watch and the optical density is measured exactly at the 10th minute. The optical density at zero time is measured for the same solution without chromic acid. The

difference gives Δx . The Δx value was determined at different oxalic acid concentrations and Δx is plotted versus [oxalic acid] (which serves as a calibration curve), which has been found to be a straight line passing through origin. The Δx value is determined for a known volume of the concentration of oxalic acid and its concentration obtained from the calibration curve.

Statistical Treatment : Five kinetic runs were carried out varying the concentration of oxalic acid, keeping the concentration of other materials constant. Δx values at the 10th minute were determined for each run. Each of the above runs was repeated six times. The standard deviation, coefficient of variation and percentage error were calculated for each of the determinations. The results are presented in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Oxalic acid taken $\mu\text{g/ml}$	Oxalic acid found $\mu\text{g/ml} \pm \text{S.D}$	No. of analyses	Coefficient of variation	Percentage error
5.04	4.96 ± 0.26	6	5.3	-1.67
7.56	7.43 ± 0.14	6	1.9	-1.67
10.08	9.91 ± 0.13	6	2.6	-1.67
12.60	12.66 ± 0.22	6	1.7	+0.50
15.12	14.99 ± 0.23	6	1.5	-0.83

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References

- (a) G. GOPALA RAO and C. R. VISWANATHAM, *Curr. Sci.*, 1942, 11, 102.
- (b) G. GOPALA RAO and C. R. VISWANATHAM, *Curr. Sci.*, 1943, 12, 186.
- (c) G. GOPALA RAO and C. R. VISWANATHAM, *Curr. Sci.*, 1944, 13, 47.
- (a) G. VANDERGRIFT and J. ROCEK, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 98, 1371.
- (b) E. HINTZE and J. ROCEK, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1977, 99, 132.
- F. FEIGL, 'Spot Tests in Organic Analysis', Elsevier Publishing Company, 1966, p. 290.